

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN CONNECTED SPEECH AND GREY MATTER CHANGES IN MILD COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT AND ALZHEIMER'S DEMENTIA

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Background. Developing new accessible strategies for the early detection and remote monitoring of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is becoming an essential aspect of clinical management. However, the biological validity of speech features in AD remains largely unknown.

Purpose. This study explored the associations between digital biomarkers derived from speech tests and changes in brain grey matter (GM) volumes assessed by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and mild AD dementia. Moreover, the associations of speech parameters with GM changes as a function of the amyloid status were analysed.

Materials and Methods: Patients with cognitive decline evaluated at the Memory Unit from Ace Alzheimer Center Barcelona underwent high-resolution T1-weighted MRI using a 3 Tesla scanner, and in a subset AD-related biomarkers were measured in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Participants completed a digital speech protocol that included describing The Cookie Theft Picture, a semantic verbal fluency test, and a description of a personal experience (~3 min). Various acoustic (n=228), lexical (n=63), semantic (n=15), syntactic (n=18), and sentiment (n=27) features were extracted from these tasks. Associations between the speech features and GM volumes defined based on the Automated Anatomical Labelling atlas were analysed using regression models adjusted by age, sex and years of formal education. The impact of speech features on GM changes based on amyloid status (CSF A β 42/A β 40 ratio <0.063; Orellana et al, 2022) was also examined. Statistical significance was set at p <0.05, adjusted for false discovery rate.

Results: The study included 240 participants: 50 with mild AD dementia (mean age 77.2, 76.0% female, mean MMSE=21.8) with positive amyloid status and 190 with MCI (mean age 72.8, 63.2% female, mean MMSE=26.7). Among the MCI group, 154 had CSF A β measurements, with 80 (52%) showing a positive amyloid status. Lower lexical density was associated with reduced GM volumes

in the inferior parietal gyri. Negative correlations were found between the number of animals named in the semantic verbal fluency test and GM volumes in the hippocampus and superior temporal gyri. Variables related to words' age of acquisition, indicative of simpler language, were consistently associated with reduced GM volumes in the parahippocampus. Acoustic and lexical features were linked to frontal regions, particularly from the personal experience task. Lower concept diversity, measured by the average cosine distance of word embeddings from the image description task, was associated with reductions in the left lingual gyrus. Semantic features based on embeddings correlated with decreases in anterior cingulate volume. Finally, in MCI patients with positive amyloid status, linguistic variables had a greater impact on GM volume reductions compared to those without amyloidosis.

Conclusion: This study provides new evidence of specific brain topographic correlations of speech-derived parameters in MCI and mild AD dementia. Our findings support the link between distinct biological changes in the brain and alterations in speech production, demonstrating the sensitivity of this digital biomarker to the impact of the amyloid status in MCI patients. These insights pave the way for developing more accessible tools for screening and monitoring cognitive decline.